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SHORT COMMUNICATION

The first report of the bow-legged fir aphid *Cinara curvipes* (Patch, 1912) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) from Ukraine

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Abstract

For the first time in Ukraine, the invasive aphid species *Cinara curvipes* is reported to have been detected in urban plantations in Bila Tserkva, Kyiv region (Ukraine) on the *Abies alba* tree.

Keywords: *Cinara curvipes*, *Abies alba*, first record, invasion, potential pest

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The bow-legged fir aphid, *Cinara curvipes* (Patch, 1912), belongs to the aphids of the subfamily Lachninae Herrich-Schaeffer, 1854. This species is native to North America, where it is distributed in its western part, from Mexico to the state of Washington and Canada. In its native range, it is associated with local fir species (e.g., *Abies magnifica* A.Murray, *A. concolor* (Gordon & Glend.) Lindl. ex Hildebr., *A. balsamea* (L.) Mill.), and some other conifers (e.g., *Cedrus deodara* (Roxb.) G.Don and *Pinus contorta* Douglas ex Loudon) (Hałaj & Osiadacz, 2015; Blackman, & Eastop, 2025; CMS Redcon, 2025).

It was first detected in the United Kingdom in Europe in 1999 (Martin, 2000). Later, it was registered in Germany (Gottschalk, 2001; Scheurer, 2001), Serbia (Poljaković-Pajnik & Petrović-Obradović, 2002), Switzerland (Angst et al., 2007), the Czech Republic (Olbrechtová, 2007; NPPO of the Czech Republic, 2008), Slovenia (Jurc et al., 2009),

Hungary (Bodor, 2013), Austria (Perny, 2014), Poland (Halaj & Osiadacz, 2015; Halaj et al., 2023), and some other European countries. However, there are no confirmed records of *C. curvipes* from Ukraine to date.

On September 28, 2025, we discovered colonies of *C. curvipes* (Fig. 1). To identify these colonies, we employed the method described by Halaj & Osiadacz (2015). The colonies were located on a single tree of *Abies alba* Mill. growing in a grove comprising ten young trees of this species. This grove is located on the bank of the Ros River, 400 m southeast of the “Olexandria” State Dendrological Park of the NAS of Ukraine. A tree infested with aphids was in a poor condition and drying out.

Two colonies of *C. curvipes*, each containing at least 200 individuals, were located on the upper part of the fir tree (Fig. 2). The colonies contained only wingless individuals. Most of them had dense waxy pubescence. Only a few

Figure 1. *Cinara curvipes* in urban plantings of Bila Tserkva (Kyiv Region, Ukraine): **A** –general view in a live state; **B** – the same, treated with 10 % KOH solution; **C** – antenna; **D** – hind tibia; **E** – siphuncular cone.

aphids were without waxy pubescence, which made them noticeable due to their shiny black backs.

The discovery of *C. curvipes* in Bila Tserkva (Kyiv Region, Ukraine) testifies to the powerful invasive abilities of this aphid species, as the reporting Ukrainian locality is

over 500 km away from the site of its closest report in Poland (Hałaj et al., 2023; Wiczorek et al., 2025). Insufficient contributions to the investigation of the invasive aphid fauna in Ukraine make it impossible to determine when aphids first entered our country and, consequently, the speed of their invasion.

Figure 2. *Cinara curvipes* colonies on the *Abies alba* tree in Bila Tserkva (Kyiv Region, Ukraine).

However, considering reports from Europe (Scheurer, 2006; Hałaj & Osiadacz, 2015; Wiczorek et al., 2025), it is reasonable to assume that this speed is very high.

Wiczorek et al. (2025) suggested that *C. curvipes* has the potential to spread to most European regions. However, the status of *C. curvipes* as a pest is still unclear. It apparently does not cause economic damage to forests in its native range in North America, but in Europe, it may have the potential to cause considerable economic damage (Dransfield & Brightwell, 2025). Further research will reveal the extent to which this pest poses a threat to the collection of fir trees in the “Olexandria” State Dendrological Park of the NAS of Ukraine.

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Перше повідомлення про знахідку *Cinara curvipes* (Patch, 1912) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) в Україні

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Уперше повідомляється про виявлення в Україні інвазійного виду попелиць *Cinara curvipes*, який було зареєстровано в міських насадженнях м. Біла Церква Київської області (Україна) на дереві *Abies alba*.

Ключові слова: *Cinara curvipes*, *Abies alba*, перша знахідка, інвазія, потенційний шкідник